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ТАДҚИҚОТ ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ | JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

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STUDY OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MULBERRY JUICE CONCENTRATE AND TRADITIONAL MULBERRY MOLASSES

ANNOTATION

Mulberry fruit (*Morus alba* L.) contains phytochemicals, including 1-deoxynojirimycin, quercetinglucoside, kaempferol-glucoside, and anthocyanins, which have antioxidant effects. The food industry increasingly uses the mulberry in food to provide human organism with precious bioactive substances. Functional food, due to the presence in its composition of valuable components, is beneficial to human health. What is more, very fast growth of mulberry causes that biomass of the plant may be used as biofuel or energy plant. The aim of this paper is to present the possibility of using the white mulberry as a raw material for functional foods and as an energy plant. Mulberry juice is a unique drink with many health benefits. It can help lift your mood and relieve stress, improve your memory and cleanse your body of parasites, quickly cure flu and colds, and even protect yourself from cancer.

Mulberries or its extracts exhibit excellent anti-microbial, anti-hyperglycaemic, anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer effects and is used to combat different acute and chronic diseases.

Key words: mulberry, chemical composition, natural juice, antioxidants, mineral and vitamin content, energy value.

TUT MEVASI SHARBATIDAN TAYYORLANGAN KONSENTRAT HAMDA AN'ANAVIY "TUT SHINNI" SINI KIMYOVIY TARKIBINI O'RGANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Tut mevasi (*Morus alba* L.) tarkibida antioksidant ta'sirga ega bo'lgan 1-deoksinojirimitsin, quercetin glyukozid, kaempferol glyukozid va antosiyaninlar kabi fitokimyoviy moddalar mavjud. Oziq-ovqat sanoati inson tanasini qimmatli biologik faol moddalar bilan ta'minlash uchun tutdan oziq-ovqat sifatida tobora ko'proq foydalanmoqda. Funktsional ovqatlanish, uning tarkibida qimmatli tarkibiy qismlar mavjudligi sababli, inson salomatligi uchun foydalidir. Bundan tashqari, tutning juda tez o'sishi o'simlikning biomassasini bioyoqilg'i yoki energiya zavodi sifatida ishlatishga imkon beradi. Minerallar organizmda sodir bo'ladigan barcha biokimyoviy jarayonlarda ishtirok etadi, qon ivish tizimining holatini va mushaklarning qisqarishini belgilaydi va barcha organlar va to'qimalarning zarur tarkibiy qismidir. Ular tanaga faqat oziq-ovqat bilan kiradi va shuning uchun ovqatlanishning muhim tarkibiy qismlari hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi tutni funktsional oziq-ovqat uchun xom ashyo va energiya manbai sifatida ishlatish imkoniyatini taqdim etishdir.

Tut sharbati sog'liq uchun juda ko'p foyda keltiradigan noyob ichimlikdir. Bu sizning kayfiyatingizni ko'tarish va stressdan xalos bo'lishga, xotirani yaxshilashga va tanani parazitlardan tozalashga, gripp va shamollashni tezda davolashga va hatto saraton kasalligidan himoya qilishga yordam beradi. Tut yoki uning ekstraktlari mukammal mikroblarga qarshi, antihiperглиsemik, antihiperlipidemik, yallig'lanishga qarshi, saratonga qarshi ta'sirga ega va turli o'tkir va surunkali kasalliklarga qarshi kurashda qo'llaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tut, kimyoviy tarkibi, tabiiy sharbat, antioksidantlar, mineral va vitamin tarkibi, energiya qiymati.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ХИМИЧЕСКОГО СОСТАВА КОНЦЕНТРАТА СОКА ПЛОДОВ ШЕЛКОВИЦЫ И ТРАДИЦИОННОЙ ПАТОКИ ШЕЛКОВИЦЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Плоды шелковицы (*Morus alba* L.) содержат фитохимические вещества, в том числе 1-дезоксиджиримизин, кверцетинглюкозид, кемпферол-глюкозид и антоцианы, которые обладают антиоксидантным действием. Пищевая промышленность все чаще использует шелковицу в пищу для обеспечения организма человека ценными биологически активными веществами. Функциональное питание благодаря наличию в его составе ценных компонентов полезно для здоровья человека. Более того, очень быстрый рост шелковицы позволяет использовать биомассу растения в качестве биотоплива или энергетической установки. Цель данной статьи – представить возможность использования шелковицы белой в качестве сырья для функциональных продуктов питания и в качестве энергетического растения. Сок шелковицы – уникальный напиток, обладающий множеством преимуществ для здоровья. Он поможет поднять настроение и снять стресс, улучшить память и очистить организм от паразитов, быстро вылечить грипп и простуду и даже защититься от рака. Шелковица или ее экстракты обладают прекрасным противомикробным, антигипергликемическим, антигиперлипидемическим, противовоспалительным, противораковым действием и используются для борьбы с различными острыми и хроническими заболеваниями.

Ключевые слова: шелковица, химический состав, натуральный сок, антиоксиданты, минеральный и витаминный состав, энергетическая ценность.

Introduction

The mulberry as a fruit with high water content and sensitive texture, is a perishable fruit with high-level waste. To reduce the losses of the white mulberry, it used to be processed traditional dried fruit and mulberry molasses. The purpose of this study was to determine chemical and physical properties of white mulberry molasses made up of different cultivars, neutralizers and concentration methods. Mulberry fruit (*Morus alba* L.) contains phytochemicals, including 1-deoxynojirimycin, quercetinglucoside, kaempferol-glucoside, and anthocyanins, which have antioxidant effects. The food industry increasingly uses the white mulberry in food to provide human organism with precious bioactive substances. Functional food, due to the presence in its composition of valuable components, is beneficial to human health. What is more, very fast growth of mulberry causes that biomass of the plant may be used as biofuel or energy plant. The aim of this paper is to present the possibility of using the white mulberry as a raw material for functional foods and as an energy plant.

Objects and Methods

Chromatography is a physicochemical separation, that is, a method for determining substances in a mixture, based on the separation of components into two immiscible phases-stationary and mobile. The stationary phase is a solid (often called a sorbent) or a liquid film deposited on an inert solid. The mobile phase is a liquid or gaseous substance passing over the surface of the stationary phase.

In chromatography, the mixture to be analyzed moves through a stationary phase along with a mobile phase. It is usually (but not always) placed in a glass (or metal) tube called a column. Depending on the force of interaction with the surface of the sorbent (due to adsorption or other mechanical force), the components move in the pipeline at different speeds. Components with a high reaction to the sorbent remain in the upper layer of the column, components with a low reaction remain in the lower layer, and some leave the column along with the mobile phase. This way the mixture is separated into its components.

Unlike other methods based on the separation of components into phases, chromatography is a dynamic method that provides several repetitions of the sorption-desorption process of the separated components in a mobile phase flow. This repeated repetition provides higher efficiency than other methods of static sorption and extraction, so chromatography allows you to quickly separate complex mixtures with chemically similar components. The advantages of chromatography are versatility, speed and high sensitivity. We determined magnesium from the finished product from meat that turned out to be stew and pate. The objects of the study were experimental versions of recipes for canned rabbit meat and ingredients of plant origin: olive cake, amaranth cake, pumpkin oil (Table 1).

Results and its discussion

Fruit juices occupy a significant share among products for the population. Their technology is distinguished by high requirements for the quality of raw materials, milder heat treatment regimes, the exclusion of direct contact (at different stages of processing) with atmospheric oxygen, as well as the ability to balance the chemical composition of the finished product. due to the introduction of natural biologically active products into the recipe. When developing production technology, modern principles of integrated use of raw materials were implemented to create multi-component food systems for specific purposes *Table 1*.

Table 1

Composition of mulberry juice, concentrate and sediment laboratory test, wt (%)

Indicators	Test results		
	Mulberry juice	Mulberry juice concentrate	centrifuge sediment
Dry matter content, %	19,5	64,4	18,8
Mass fraction of sucrose, mg /100 ml	5,56	25,37	30,17
Titrateable acidity calculated as citric acid, %	1,45	1,62	1,18
Mass fraction of magnesium, Mg ²⁺ , mg/ml	0,0005	0,0009	0,0002
Mass fraction of potassium, K ⁺ , mg/ml	0,0035	0,0042	0,0017
Mass fraction of sodium, Na ⁺ , mg/ml	0,0016	0,0019	0,0012
Mass fraction of calcium, Ca ⁺ , mg/ml	0,0008	0,0011	0,0003

Vitamins, mg/ml:			
Vitamin C	0,14	0,74	0,5
Vitamin B ₁	0,13	1.26	0,32
Vitamin B ₂	-	-	-
Vitamin B ₆	0,24	0,10	0,22
Vitamin PP	0,04	0,43	0,03
Heavy metals: mg/kg			
mass fraction of copper	0,0206	0,0550	0,0188
mass fraction of lead	Not found	Not found	Not found
mass fraction of iron	0,0431	0,1872	0,0189
mass fraction of cadmium	0,0020	0,0012	0,0024
mass fraction of nickel	Not found	Not found	Not found
mass fraction of arsenic	Not found	Not found	Not found
5-oxymethylfurfural	-	Not found	-

As can be seen from the table, the refractometric content of dry substances in mulberry juice is 19.5%, of which 18% are sugars. This is more than the dry matter in apple (12-14%), pomegranate (10-16%), tomato (4-9%) juices, so mulberry fruits are rich in sugars. There are heavy metals such as lead, iron, cadmium and nickel, the amount of which is below the permissible concentration (MAC). Hydroxymethylfurfural was not formed due to the low evaporation temperature.

Figure.1. Chromatographic analysis of sucrose determined in clarified mulberry juice diagram below.

Peak of the chromatogram in Fig. 1 shows that the sucrose content in the juice, centrifuged for 1.5-2.0 minutes, was 5.56%

The data obtained and their analysis made it possible to select the most optimal option for traditional mulberry molasses., which will be in demand and competitive with other types of products in the product range. Traditional mulberry molasses prepared in the laboratory gave good results in terms of both vitamin and toxicological composition.

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